

MEDICAL SCIENCES

AXONAL CONNECTIONS OF RETICULAR NEURONS WITH CEREBELLUM AND SPINAL CORD IN FROGS

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Abstract

The motor activity of the organism is the main point of interest in our research. Especially, it's interesting to study amphibians' movements structures as they are the lowest vertebrates, and their structures are least differentiated. It's important to understand the regulatory mechanisms of the movements and their evolutionary development. In scope of this study was interaction between medial reticular formation (MRF) neurons and auricular lobe of cerebellum. This electrophysiological study was performed on the frogs by the isolated perfused brain technique via intracellular recording of the neurons action potentials. The results showed that the stimulation of ipsilateral vestibular nerve caused mono- and polysynaptic action potentials of the studied reticular neurons. The stimulation of auricular lobe of cerebellum caused inhibitory postsynaptic potentials of the above-mentioned neurons. By directing the motor act, the cerebellum is actively involved in the regulation of posture and movements of various types, cooperating not only with the vestibular system but also with the reticular system of the brainstem.

Keywords: intracellular recording, reticular formation, cerebellum, spinal cord.

Introduction. The motor activity of the organism is the result of a complex interaction of the motor structures of the brain and spinal cord. Neurons of the two main descending pathways (vestibulo- and reticulospinal) are closely interconnected and, obviously, this connection directly affects the regulation of the organism's movements. Most reticulospinal neurons, regardless of their localization in the brainstem, participate in the transmission of vestibular information to the spinal cord. Thus, neurons of the medial reticular formation (MRF) together with vestibular neurons influence the motor neurons of the spinal cord, regulating the interaction between the integration and execution of movements [2]. Since the motor structures of amphibians are the least differentiated, it is important to study their functional interaction. This work combines the results of cerebellar-reticular and reticulospinal relationships.

Material and methods. The experiments were carried out on 93 marsh frogs (*Rana ridibunda*) of both sexes using the isolated perfused brain technique. The animals were anesthetized with MS-222 solution (0.2 g/kg). The chest was opened, and the heart was exposed. A cannula was introduced through its ventricle into the aortic arch for perfusion with Ringer's solution for cold-blooded animals saturated with carbogen (10°-15° C). Electrical stimulation of the anterior branch of the VIII nerve was performed by single direct current shocks (0.1-0.2 msec; 0.05-0.1 mA) using a silver suction electrode. The cerebellum was also opened by craniotomy. Bipolar ball electrodes were carefully applied to the surface of the auricular region under visual control. For electrical stimulation of the auricular region of the cerebellum, the same current parameters were used as for the vestibular nerve. For intracellular recording of the electrical activity of the MRF neurons, ground

glass microelectrodes filled with a 2 M potassium citrate solution with a resistance of 10 MΩ were used. Stimulation of the reticulospinal tract in the areas of the cervical and lumbar thickenings was carried out with bipolar tungsten electrodes. Computer analysis of the data was carried out using the Origin 8.5 and NiDiadem programs. The arithmetic means standard deviations of the indicators are given.

Results and discussion. Neurons of the MRF were identified based on excitatory postsynaptic potentials (EPSPs) (Fig. 1, a 1, b 1, c 1, d 1; Fig. 2, a 1, b 1, c 1, d 1), arising during stimulation of the ipsilateral vestibular nerve and their activation during stimulation of the cervical and lumbar spinal cord.

A single stimulation of the auricular region of the cerebellar cortex caused inhibitory postsynaptic potentials (IPSPs). Only 30% of all neurons of the MRF identified through vestibular nerve stimulation responded to stimulation of the cerebellum. Intracellular activity of 175 reticular neurons was recorded. Considering the temporal characteristics of the studied responses, we conditionally divided the recorded IPSPs into two groups: short-latency and long-latency.

The first group included 56 neurons, the latent period of which was 1.65-3.0 msec (on average 2.56±0.33 msec; n=56) (Fig. 1, A, a 2, b 2; Fig. 2). With different stimulation intensities, no significant change was observed in the duration of the latent period and the time of increase in amplitude to the maximum. The latter was on average 3.72±0.93 msec (2.1-6.15 msec; n=52). Their amplitude reached 0.57-3.3 mV (on average 1.58±0.58 mV; n=52). The total duration varied within 7.46-22.5 msec (mean 11.6±3.16; n=55) (Fig. 1, A, a 2, b 2; Fig. 2). The noted indicators provided grounds for considering these IPSP as monosynaptic [7].

Fig.1. Postsynaptic potentials of medial reticular neurons in response to stimulation of the ipsilateral auricular region of cerebellar cortex.

A, a2, b2 – monosynaptic, B a2, b2 – polysynaptic IPSPs, at different intensity of stimulation of the auricular region of cerebellar cortex.

A, a1, b1, B, a1, b1 – EPSPs of the same reticular neurons to stimulation of the anterior branch of the vestibular nerve to identification.

Short-latency IPSPs were generated monosynaptically in the neurons of the RF, presumably by direct activation of Purkinje cell axons projecting to the MRF, like the existing direct connection of Purkinje cells with the vestibular nuclei [6].

The second group included 119 reticular neurons in which stimulation of the auricular region of the cerebellar cortex evoked IPSPs with a longer and more unstable latent period (Fig. 1, B a 2, b 2; Fig. 2). They were characterized by a clear shortening of the latent period and the time of increase in IPSP hyperpolarization to the maximum with an increase in stimulation intensity. Their latent period fluctuated within 3.04-6.0

msec (average 4.2 ± 0.8 msec; $n=119$). The duration of the amplitude rise time to the maximum averaged 5.16 ± 1.24 ms (2.22-8 msec; $n=87$). The amplitude reached its maximum at an average of 1.8 ± 0.62 mV (0.63-3.5 mV; $n=92$). The total duration of these IPSPs was within 8.18-27.8 msec (on average 15.5 ± 4.6 msec; $n=112$) (Fig. 1, B a 2, b 2; Fig. 2). The above-mentioned temporal characteristics of the recorded IPSPs and their dependence on the stimulation intensity indicate their polysynaptic origin.

It was found that long-latency IPSPs evoked by weak stimulation of the cerebellar surface gradually shortened in time with increasing stimulation intensity, i.e., with spatial summation of parallel fiber inputs to the Purkinje cell dendrites. The described polysynaptic IPSPs arose not by direct, but by indirect activation of Purkinje cells through parallel fibers, by analogy with those recorded in the VNC in response to stimulation of the auricular region of the cerebellar cortex [6].

Fig. 2. Histogram of the distribution of mono- and polysynaptic IPSPs of the medial reticular formation neurons in response to stimulation of the ipsilateral auricular region of cerebellar cortex. The broken line conventionally separates mono- and polysynaptic responses.

The IPSP latency depends not only on the stimulation intensity, but also on the localization of the stimulating electrode, since some neurons respond monosynaptically with very weak stimulation, while others require a strong stimulus. The frequency of occurrence of the noted IPSPs decreased when the stimulating electrode was moved closer to the midline of the cerebellum.

In response to stimulation of the cervical and lumbar spinal cord at different stimulation intensities, antidromic action potentials with a short and fixed latent

period arose. They were distinguished by their short refractoriness and the ability to reproduce high-frequency stimulation (Fig. 3. A 3, B 3). Reticular neurons that were activated only by stimulation of the cervical spinal cord were designated as C-neurons, and neurons that were also activated by stimulation of the lumbar spinal cord were designated as L-neurons. Fig. 3. A 1, B1 shows action potentials based on which all the subsequent data were registered.

Fig. 3. Antidromic activation of the reticulospinal neurons in response to stimulation of cervical and lumbar spinal cord.

A1, B1 - action potentials of reticulospinal neurons in response to stimulation of the vestibular nerve. A 2, B 2 - antidromic responses to stimulation of the cervical and lumbar spinal cord, respectively. A 3, B 3 - responses of the same neurons to high-frequency stimulation of the spinal cord. C, D - histograms of the distribution of latent periods of C- and L-neurons, respectively.

The latent period of C-neurons was within 0.37-1.66 msec. The latent period of L-neurons was 0.51-1.8 msec (Fig. 3. A 2, B 2, C, D). The distance between the sites of C and L stimulation was 5-14 mm (on average 9.84 ± 1.44 ; $n=55$). The distance between the microelectrode insertion site into the brain and the stimulation site of the cervical spinal cord for reticulospinal neurons was 3-6.9 mm (mean 4.63 ± 0.7 ; $n=211$) [1, 4, 5].

Based on axonal conduction velocities, reticular neurons were divided into slow - up to 14 m/sec and fast - 15 m/sec and higher. Slow and fast reticular C and L neurons were recorded in all areas of the MRF. It was found that there were more slow C neurons than fast ones [4].

Conclusion. The brainstem of frogs is relatively simple and less differentiated. The reticular formation is less compartmentalized, lacks clear functional nuclei differentiation and its neurons tend to be more homogeneous and diffusely distributed while in mammals it's highly developed and compartmentalized. But despite

all anatomical and functional differences the reticular formation of amphibians plays great role in the movement's realization like in mammals. The cerebellum is actively involved in the regulation of posture and movements of various types, cooperating not only with the vestibular system but also with the reticular system of the brainstem [3, 4]. The axons of the frog's reticulospinal neurons monosynaptically contact the motor neurons of the cervical and lumbar enlargements. This proves that although the reticular neurons are localized in small groups, compared to the vestibular ones, they significantly affect body movements. All the above indicates the important role of the reticulospinal neurons in the mediation of vestibular influences on spinal motor mechanisms.

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